

ROR for Publishers

October 27, 2023

What is ROR?

The [Research Organization Registry \(ROR\)](#) is a global, community-led registry of open persistent identifiers for research organizations operated and sustained by Crossref, DataCite, and the California Digital Library. [Learn more about ROR's history, scope and governance.](#)

ROR includes identifiers and metadata for more than 100,000 organizations. ROR identifiers are designed to link research organizations to research outputs in scholarly infrastructure. [Search the ROR registry.](#)

Designed for **research workflows**

How do publishers use ROR?

Academic publishers use ROR to help ensure that author/reviewer/editor affiliation and funding organization information is entered consistently, so that contributions from users affiliated with or funded by a particular organization can be easily identified.

ROR not only helps to streamline internal workflows; as an open identifier, it's ideal for inclusion in DOI metadata submitted to Crossref.

When affiliations and ROR IDs are included in DOI metadata, the entire scholarly community can leverage that information to automate reporting and gain insight into research outputs at the institutional level.

How can ROR IDs help?

- **Administrative operations:** Streamline administrative workflows, such as managing institutional APCs, by accurately identifying author affiliations.
- **Metrics/analytics:** Gain more accurate insight into which institutions are represented by your authors, reviewers, editors, and subscribers.
- **Enriching the scholarly community:** Allow the entire scholarly community to gain insight into research outputs at the institutional level by exposing affiliation information in DOI metadata submitted to Crossref or DataCite.

ROR integration points for publishers

Submission/review

Match ROR IDs to author, reviewer and editor affiliations AND to funder organizations in your submission/review systems:

- **For new submissions/registrations:** [Add typeahead fields](#) to your forms for manuscript submission or user registration that are populated using ROR data.
- **For existing affiliation information in your system:** [Match institution names to ROR IDs](#) using our matching tools (don't forget to update metadata for existing DOIs with ROR IDs!).

DOI registration

Both Crossref and DataCite now support ROR IDs in DOI metadata. Include ROR IDs in author affiliation and funding information fields to allow the entire scholarly community to leverage ROR in reporting and discovery:

- When you register content with Crossref or DataCite, include ROR IDs in DOI metadata. See [Include ROR IDs in Crossref DOIs](#) and [Include ROR IDs in DataCite DOIs](#).
- If you update existing affiliation/funder organization information in your system to include ROR IDs, be sure to update your DOI metadata.

Organization lists

Do you have an internal organization list that you use for billing, agreements and other administrative workflows?

- If your lists(s) include other global organization ID types such as Crossref Funder ID, GRID, ISNI, OrgRef or Wikidata, you can find the corresponding ROR IDs for those IDs. See [Map other ID types to ROR](#).
- If you're currently using GRID in your organization lists, it's important to know that GRID has ended its public releases in Q4 2021. See [GRID/ROR Transition FAQ](#).
- If you are using Crossref Funder IDs to identify funders of published research outputs, it's important to know that the Crossref Funder Registry

will cease to have public releases sometime after 2024. See [Open Funder Registry to transition into Research Organisation Registry](#).

- If your lists include organization names, but no IDs, you can find corresponding ROR IDs for those names. See [Match organization names to ROR IDs](#).